

Antibody Characterization Report for Fetuin-B

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

Author(s): Riham Ayoubi¹, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Target:

Recommended protein name: Fetuin-B

Alternative protein name: 16G2, Fetuin-like protein IRL685, Gugu

Gene name: *FETUB*

Uniprot ID: human: Q9UGM5, mouse: Q9QXC1

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science¹. In this study, we characterized two Fetuin-B commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol^{2,3} based on comparing read-outs in knockout (KO) samples and isogenic parental controls (wild-type; WT). We identified well-performing mouse reactive antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. Evidence of Fetuin-B secretion in serum is shown elsewhere⁴. WT and *FETUB* KO sera from mouse were kindly donated by Dr. Willi Jahnen-Dechent at RWTH Aachen University, Germany.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the Fetuin-B antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications	Species reactivity (from vendors)
GeneTex	GTX112260	41808	AB_11172475	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.31	Wb, IP, IF	H, M, R
R&D Systems	AF1725	JNJ0107081	AB_2103184	polyclonal	-	goat	0.20	Wb	H, M, R
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-29468	WL3464978A	AB_2546944	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.31	Wb, IP, IF	H, M, R

Wb=western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, H=human, M=mouse, R=rat

Note: GTX112260 and PA5-29468 appear to be a cross licensed product.

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the Fetuin-B antibodies tested are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120). Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-goat is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A15999).

Antibody screening by western blot on mouse serum

WT and *FETUB* KO (listed in Table 1) sera from mouse were analyzed by SDS-PAGE, and western blot was performed as described in our standard operating procedure³. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used. Briefly, samples were processed on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Figure 1: Fetuin-B antibody screening by western blot on mouse serum

Figure 1: Fetuin-B antibody screening by western blot on mouse serum.

30 µg of WT and *FETUB* KO serum from mouse were processed for western blot with the indicated Fetuin-B antibodies. The Ponceau stained protein transfers of each blot are shown. All antibodies were used at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 42 kDa.

References

- 1 Laflamme, C., Edwards, A. M., Bandrowski, A. E. & McPherson, P. S. Opinion: Independent third-party entities as a model for validation of commercial antibodies. *N Biotechnol* **65**, 1-8 (2021). <https://doi.org:10.1016/j.nbt.2021.07.001>
- 2 Laflamme, C. *et al.* Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife* **8** (2019). <https://doi.org:10.7554/eLife.48363>
- 3 Ayoubi, R., Ryan, J., Bolivar, S. G. & Lalamme, C. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Protocol Exchange* (2024). <https://doi.org:https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1>
- 4 Denecke, B. *et al.* Tissue distribution and activity testing suggest a similar but not identical function of fetuin-B and fetuin-A. *Biochem J* **376**, 135-145 (2003). <https://doi.org:Doi 10.1042/Bj20030676>